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Review Article

Herbal Mouthwash For The Management Of Oral Diseases

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ABSTRACT

Several different varieties of mouthwashes are accessible to us nowadays, including chemical as well as herbal formulations. Appropriate mouthwash can be selected depending on the oral condition, risk, and efficiency of mouthwash. Mouthwash is an aqueous solution that is most commonly used for plaque control. It is a medicated liquid that is held in the mouth and swished by the action of perioral musculature to eliminate oral pathogens. Herbal medicine takes a preventive approach. The main advantage of these natural herbs is that no side effects have been reported to date. Aside from that, all herbal mouthwash Wash is free of alcohol and or sugar. Nowadays people may face more oral problems like periodontal disease, sore throat, gingivitis, and plaque. For maintaining good oral health various formulations are formulated. A mouthwash is recommended for controlling plaque, bad breath, toothache, and bacteria. Herbal Mouthwash is preferred over chemical mouthwash as it shows fewer side effects and is non-irritant and less toxic. Herbal mouthwash consists of extracts of Crude drugs which have no or fewer side effects as compared to synthetic mouthwash. Herbal mouthwashes are prepared from various plant extracts. Mouthwash is a liquid that is held in the mouth passively or swilled around the mouth by contraction of the Perioral muscles and/or movement of the head and maybe gargled, where the head is tilted back and the Liquid bubbled at the back of the mouth. Oral healthcare professionals would find this review helpful for accurate mouthwash selection while dealing with different conditions of the oral cavity.

INTRODUCTION

The primary aim of this review is to find an alternative mouthwash - A gold standard

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mouthwash that is prescribed by most dentists during treatments like gingival inflammation and periodontal diseases. Susceptibility to dental and periodontal disease depends on risk factors including genetics, systemic factors, and oral hygiene. Mouthwashes are an antiseptic solution that is used to reduce the microbial load in the oral cavity. Mouth rinses can deliver a therapeutic effect all over the tooth surface including interproximal areas in which even toothpastes are not very effective. Mouthwashes are liquids that contain anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and analgesic action. There are two types of mouthwash - chemical and herbal. The main purposes of using mouthwash are it can be used at home as a routine to maintain good oral hygiene, mouthwash provides anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial activity.¹ Mouthwash is a liquid that is passively held in the mouth or swilled around the Mouth by contraction of the perioral muscles and movement of the head, and it may be gargled, in which the head is tilted back and the liquid bubbles at the back of the mouth. Herbal mouthwashes can be used in conjunction with other oral hygiene practices such as tooth brushing and flossing. It is free of alcohol, artificial preservatives, flavors, and colors. Hence Herbal mouthwashes can Be used in place of chemical mouthwashes to maintain oral hygiene, owing to the additional benefits provided by herbal Preparations²

Advantage: 3

1. Fresh breath.
2. Reducing tooth decay using sodium fluoride.
3. Reducing gum inflammation by killing bacteria.
4. Whitening teeth using a bleaching agent.
5. Preventing gum disease using an antiseptic or anti-plaque ingredient.
6. Mouthwash prevents gingivitis and gum disease by killing the bacteria that would otherwise infect the dental sockets and gums.

7. It can prevent the build-up of plaque, strengthen the enamel, and demineralize your teeth, allowing You to prevent tooth decay

Types of Herbal mouthwash⁴

Fluoride mouthwash:

Fluoride in mouthwashes contains salt which helps protect the teeth from cavities and cavities. Since fluoride can also be found in toothpaste and water, it's advisable to require care when using this type of mouthwash since intake of an excessive amount of fluoride isn't good for your overall health.

Antiseptic mouthwash:

This is the foremost common mouthwash. This mouthwash usually contains alcohol and is typically utilized by people with mouth infections to stop bacterial growth. This is often also helpful for people who have halitosis or bad breath. This is often used alongside the proper brushing of teeth and flossing to help forbid bacteria that cause mouth infections and stinky breath.

Cosmetic mouthwash:

A mouthwash that doesn't do anything to your overall oral care but is just how to freshen your breath or mask bad breath.

Natural mouthwash:

Natural mouthwash could also be a mouthwash that does what other sorts of mouthwash do except the ingredients are natural. It is also a popular option as an alcohol-free mouthwash. Their ingredients are safer to use as compared to other sorts of mouthwash.

Effects of Mouthwash Production:

Commercial antiseptic mouthwashes are the most widely used mouthwashes and are used at home as part of a dental hygiene practice. To treat several oral disorders, mouthwashes mix various substances. Because of the frequent variations and lack of a standardized composition, mouthwash use and recommendations raise patient safety issues. Some mouthwash producers claim that the bacterial plaque in their antiseptic and antiplaque mouthwashes is destroyed, preventing cavities,

gingivitis, and foul breath. Mouthwash side effects, such as taste, are frequently minor and temporary if the person is allergic or sensitive to mouthwash chemicals, such as preservatives, colors, flavors, and scents (for example, aphthous

stomatitis or allergic contact stomatitis). By diluting the mouthwash with water, switching to a different mouthwash (such as salt water), or forgoing mouthwash entirely, these effects may be diminished or eliminated.

Traditional herbal medicinal plants used as Herbal mouthwash 6-7

Plants	Parts Of Plants	Bioactive Components	Medicinal Use
Guava	Branches	Saponins, tannins, flavonoids and alkaloids	Strong, clean, fresh, and free of plaque and cavities
Neem	leaves	Gallotannin	Antibacterial, antiseptic, insecticide
Tulsi	leaves	Linalol, Eugenol	tooth disease mouth ulcers and infections
Liquorice	Root	Flavonoids, Glycyrrhizin	Glycyrrhiza Glabara
Cinnamon	Bark	Cinnamic acid, Cinnamaldehyde	Flavoring agent, Bacteriocidal
Clove	Flower bud	Flavonoids, Hydroxycinnamic acids	Analgesic, Anti-inflammatory
Green tea	Leaves	Epigallocatechin gallate	Tooth decay, bad breath, laryngitis, stomatitis, plaque build-up, sore throat
Mentha	Leaves	carvone, limonene, cis-dihydrocarvone,	Antibacterial
Anise	fruit	trans-anethole, estragole	Breath Freshening
Lavender	flower	linalool, linalyl acetate, terpinen-4-ol, acetate lavandulol, oci-mene, cineole	Antibacterial
Perforate St John's-wort	Stem	hyperforin, naphthodianthrones, flavonoids,	Anti-inflammatory

The most common evidence-based effects of mouthwash on subgingival biofilms include the inhibition of biofilm accumulation and their anti-gingivitis effect. There has been no significant change in the strength of the evidence over the last decade. There is strong evidence for the effects of CHG and EO mouthwash. Fluoride mouthwash contributes to caries prevention and arrest, with high-quality evidence for its effectiveness in children and limited evidence for its role in root-carries management fig.1

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of the clinical effects of mouthwashes against supragingival dental biofilm with strong evidence.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PROSPECTIVE

This review highlights the variety of mouthwashes that can be prescribed depending on the oral diseases. Hence, oral healthcare practitioners must be cognizant of various etiologic factors and predisposing conditions of the oral cavity. The formulated herbal mouthwashes can significantly Work in a long way to help people eradicate dental Issues such as decay, gingivitis, sensitive teeth, root Infection, bad breath, enamel erosions, and many other oral problems. Furthermore, we can assure you that No harmful ingredients are present in mouthwash Formulations.⁹ The herbal mouthwash is better than Chlorhexidine mouthwash as it does not because negative Herbal mouthwashes are suitable for maintaining good oral prophylaxis. Many programs have to be conducted to make them aware of mouthwashes in their oral hygiene According to the World Health Organization, more than 80% of the world's population depends on traditional medicine for their primary healthcare needs. Mouthwash formulations are frequently prescribed by dentists for the prevention and treatment of pathologic conditions in the mouth. However, the market offers a wide variety of mouth rinses that are freely used by patients without medical supervision. The application of miswak in dentistry dates back to 5000 B.C. when January was reported to have been extensively used by Babylonians, Arabians, and Muslims. Miswak was proven to be efficient in reducing plaque score and cariogenic bacterial count as it has antipyretic, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic properties. Thus, it was recommended for use in mouthwash formulations with good antimicrobial effectiveness of herbal-based mouth rinses against oral microorganisms¹⁰

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